

Screening of microorganisms capable of acephate degradation

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Organophosphates (OPs) are esters of phosphoric acid and phosphorothioic acid. They are powerful inhibitors of acetylcholinesterase (found in nervous tissues and erythrocytes) which results in accumulation of substrate acetylcholine leading to several health issues. Among several organophosphates, acephate is one of the most widely used and toxic pesticide. Acephate ($C_4H_{10}NO_3PS$) is an organophosphate insecticide which is registered under The Insecticide Act, 1968 to be used on rice, safflower and cotton. But it is highly misused due to lack of proper knowledge regarding its use. Also, being water soluble it can be retained in environment for longer period of time. According to Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), acephate continuously stimulates the central nervous system resulting in dizziness, nausea, confusion, respiratory paralysis at very high exposures (e.g., accidents or major spills) and death in severe cases. Basically, three methods are utilized for the degradation of xenobiotic compounds, i.e., physical, chemical and biological degradation. The physicochemical approaches are generally expensive, often leading to the formation of the end products which are more persistent and equally or more toxic as compared to parent compound. Thus, bioremediation is preferred. Biodegradation of inorganic and organic pollutants occurs through stimulation of indigenous microbial population which help in conversion of the harmful compounds in less toxic products. The present study focusses upon the acephate degradation by microbes isolated from soil. Nine microbial cultures were isolated on the basis of their growth on acephate. Degradation was studied using plate assay followed by broth assay. Percentage degradation was recorded by UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

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